

Morphing Cholinesterase Inhibitor Amiridine into Multipotent Drugs for the Treatment of Alzheimer's Disease

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1. Synthesis of intermediates **8**, **11** and **12**

Derivatives **8**, **11** and **12** were prepared by a slightly modified method from [1]. **General procedure:** Solution of 2-chloroacetyl chloride (4 eq) in chloroform (0.25 M) was added dropwise to cooled (ice bath) solution of amiridine, 1-adamantylamine (**9**) or memantine (**10**) (1 eq) in chloroform (0.43 M). The reaction mixture was stirred at 90 °C overnight. The reaction was monitored by TLC with mobile phases DCM/MeOH/NH₃ (9/1/0.1) for **8**, DCM/MeOH/NH₃ (50/1/0.1) for **11** and **12** (the spots on TLCs were visualized using a solution of phosphomolybdic acid). After cooling to room temperature, the mixture was washed with 5% (w/v) aqueous solution of NaHCO₃ and then with brine. The organic solvent was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and evaporated under reduced pressure with the residual 2-chloroacetyl chloride. The crude product was purified by column chromatography. NMR spectra of **8**, **11** and **12** were in agreement with previously published data.[1–3]

*2-Chloro-N-{1H,2H,3H,5H,6H,7H,8H-cyclopenta[b]quinolin-9-yl}acetamide (**8**):* Isolated as white solid (1.53 g, 54%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 7.92 (s, 1H), 4.16 (s, 2H), 2.93 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 2.84 (t, *J* = 6.3 Hz, 2H), 2.75 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 2.53 (t, *J* = 6.2 Hz, 2H), 2.03 (p, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.72–1.81 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): 164.2, 163.4, 156.5, 137.9, 130.1, 123.7, 42.8, 34.5, 32.7, 29.8, 24.3, 23.0, 22.7, 22.5 ppm. HRMS [M+H]⁺: 265.11011 (calculated for [C₁₄H₁₈ClN₂O]⁺: 265.11022).

*N-(adamantan-1-yl)-2-chloroacetamide (**11**):* Isolated as colorless crystals (542 mg, 90%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 6.15 (s, 1H), 3.86 (s, 2H), 2.03–2.04 (m, 3H), 1.93–1.96 (m, 6H), 1.60–1.63 (m, 6H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ 164.6, 52.4, 42.9, 41.3, 36.2, 29.4 ppm.

*2-Chloro-N-(3,5-dimethyladamantan-1-yl)acetamide (**12**):* Isolated as brown oil (684 mg, 52%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 6.17 (s, 1H), 3.85 (s, 2H), 2.10 (p, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 1.79–1.80 (m, 2H), 1.62 (ddt, *J* = 12.1, 2.4, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 1.57 (ddt, *J* = 11.7, 2.4, 1.2 Hz, 2H), 1.31–1.35 (m, 2H), 1.24 (dtd, *J* = 12.5, 2.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 1.10 (qt, *J* = 12.4, 2.1 Hz, 2H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ 164.7, 54.0, 50.5, 47.2, 42.5, 39.8, 32.4, 30.1, 30.0 ppm.

2. Inhibition of cholinesterases

The evaluation of inhibition activities of novel compounds against human recombinant AChE (*hAChE*; E.C. 3.1.1.7) and human serum BChE (*hBChE*, E.C. 3.1.1.8) was determined following the modified spectrophotometric protocol of Ellman *et al.*[4] Final compounds **5–7** were primary tested at concentration of 1 μM, then IC₅₀ values were assessed for selected derivatives. The percentages of inhibition and IC₅₀ values (of **5c-d**, **7c** and **7g**) are summarized in Table S1. Amiridine and THA were used as reference compounds.

Table S1. Inhibition activities of 5–7 and reference compounds (amiridine hydrochloride and THA).

Name	Structure	<i>h</i> AChE ± SEM ^a (%) c = 1 × 10 ⁻⁶ M (IC ₅₀)	<i>h</i> BChE ± SEM ^a (%) c = 1 × 10 ⁻⁶ M (IC ₅₀)
5a		2.83 ± 0.49	14.01 ± 1.75
5b		9.13 ± 0.48	18.61 ± 0.65
5c		1.53 ± 0.38	62.66 ± 0.16 (IC ₅₀ = 0.6 ± 0.02 μM)
5d		5.23 ± 0.25	95.16 ± 0.06 (IC ₅₀ = 0.1 ± 0.004 μM)
6		3.95 ± 0.25	21.52 ± 0.94
7a		1.46 ± 0.17	7.19 ± 0.91
7b		18.48 ± 0.37	10.83 ± 0.09
7c		15.71 ± 1.17	25.00 ± 2.39 (IC ₅₀ = 4.9 ± 0.35 μM)
7d		1.80 ± 0.33	6.73 ± 0.45
7e		13.30 ± 0.57	13.92 ± 0.60
7f		12.13 ± 1.21	12.96 ± 0.44
7g		11.89 ± 0.74	26.46 ± 1.45 (IC ₅₀ = 11 ± 1.2 μM)
7h		4.68 ± 1.48	9.26 ± 0.68
7i		7.98 ± 0.99	0.93 ± 0.08

7j		8.20 ± 0.41	8.03 ± 1.37
7k		9.62 ± 0.41	4.47 ± 0.58
7l		7.56 ± 0.38	6.05 ± 1.77
7m		13.28 ± 0.71	1.50 ± 0.64
Amiridine.HCl^b		($IC_{50} = 4.44 \pm 0.36 \mu M$)	($IC_{50} = 0.18 \pm 0.01 \mu M$)
THA^c		($IC_{50} = 0.32 \pm 0.013 \mu M$)	($IC_{50} = 0.08 \pm 0.001 \mu M$)

^a Results are expressed as the mean of at least three experiments; ^b taken from reference [1]; ^c taken from reference [5].

3. Cytotoxicity and BBB permeation estimation according to PAMPA

The cytotoxic profile of **5–7** was carried out by MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay on human neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y) and hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell lines as described previously.[6] The cytotoxicity of all the novel compounds was assessed on the SH-SY5Y cells in undifferentiated and in differentiated form. The data obtained from the measurements on the undifferentiated cells are summarized in Table S2, while the measurements on differentiated cells are shown on Figure S1.

To investigate the possibility of **5–7** to cross the BBB and thus potentially be CNS active drugs, we used two tools, a parallel artificial membrane permeation assay (PAMPA) and an algorithm called “BBB score”.[7–9] The results of final derivatives and reference compounds (amiridine.HCl and THA) for PAMPA are shown in Table S2.

Table S2. Cytotoxicity profiles of **5–7** on SH-SY5Y cell line and predictions to BBB penetration by PAMPA results.

Name	Structure	Cytotoxicity $IC_{50} \pm SEM (\mu M)$		BBB permeation estimation	
		SH-SY5Y	HepG2	$P_e \pm SEM$ ($10^{-6} \text{ cm.s}^{-1}$) ^a	CNS (+/-) ^b
5a		74.02 ± 2.80	67.89 ± 1.12	23.35 ± 1.86	CNS +

5b		31.02 ± 2.76	19.54 ± 1.72	7.63 ± 0.09	CNS +
5c		≥ 200	186.69 ± 11.66	1.63 ± 0.19	CNS -
5d		112.45 ± 1.45	41.57 ± 3.51	2.23 ± 0.05	CNS +/-
6		≥ 200	n.d. ^c	15.93 ± 0.38	CNS +
7a		72.31 ± 6.89	≥ 200	20.64 ± 0.44	CNS +
7b		≥ 200	≥ 200	3.74 ± 0.36	CNS +/-
7c		17.68 ± 2.34	21.61 ± 0.21	2.13 ± 1.04	CNS +/-
7d		111.40 ± 5.60	14.47 ± 1.84	2.62 ± 0.00	CNS +/-
7e		77.35 ± 4.54	26.41 ± 1.82	13.90 ± 1.26	CNS +
7f		145.57 ± 14.48	≥ 200	2.17 ± 0.04	CNS +/-
7g		98.24 ± 5.74	≥ 200	2.80 ± 0.79	CNS +/-
7h		9.52 ± 1.85	31.27 ± 3.48	1.94 ± 0.37	CNS -
7i		91.27 ± 11.02	≥ 200	4.89 ± 1.50	CNS +
7j		93.73 ± 5.38	25.83 ± 0.25	1.83 ± 0.54	CNS -
7k		51.04 ± 8.56	≥ 200	1.12 ± 0.62	CNS -
7l		172.55 ± 17.55	≥ 200	2.65 ± 0.01	CNS +/-

7m		29.51 ± 2.30	≥ 200	2.54 ± 0.42	CNS +/-
Amiridine.HCl		597.47 ± 25.49	n.d. ^c	5.8 ± 0.5	CNS +
THA		122.25 ± 1.59	168.47 ± 3.63 ^d	6.0 ± 0.6	CNS +
Furosemide		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	0.02 ± 0.07 ^e	CNS -
Chlorothiazide		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	1.1 ± 0.5 ^e	CNS -
Ranitidine		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	0.04 ± 0.02 ^e	CNS -
Donepezil		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	21.9 ± 2.1	CNS +
Rivastigmine		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	20.0 ± 2.1	CNS +
Ibuprofen		n.d. ^c	n.d. ^c	18.0 ± 4.3	CNS +

^a Results are expressed as the mean of at least two experiments; ^b classification of the prediction to cross the BBB, CNS +: high BBB permeation predicted with P_e (10^{-6} cm.s⁻¹) > 4.0, CNS -: low BBB permeation predicted with P_e (10^{-6} cm.s⁻¹) < 2.0, CNS +/-: BBB permeation uncertain with P_e (10^{-6} cm.s⁻¹) from 4.0 to 2.0; ^c n.d. = not determined; ^d taken from reference ; ^e taken from reference [10].

Figure S1. The viability of differentiated SH-SY5Y cells treated with tested compounds in the concentration corresponding to the IC₅₀ values obtained on normal (undifferentiated) SH-SY5Y cells.

4. BBB Score and Drug-Likeness

To explore the drug-likeness of our compounds, we compute BBB score according to Gupta *et al.*, and used SwissADME website tool (<http://www.swissadme.ch/index.php>) to add other in silico pharmacokinetic and drug-like properties. Our focus was on gastrointestinal absorption (GIA), Lipinski's rule of five, bioavailability, and PAINS violations (Pan Assay Interference Structures). The results are shown in Table S3. The bioavailability radar charts of all final derivatives are displayed on Figure S2.

Table S3. Summary of selected in silico pharmacokinetic properties and drug-likeness of K2508–K2525 using various rules and prediction models.

Compound	GIA ^a	BBB score ^b	Lipinski ^c	Bio. Score ^d	PAINS ^e	Bioavailability Violations
5a	High	4.8	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
5b	High	4.8	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
5c	High	4.9	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
5d	High	4.8	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
6	High	3.5	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7a	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7b	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7c	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7d	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7e	High	3.5	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7f	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7g	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7h	High	4.1	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7i	Low	2.9	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity Nitro group ^f
7j	Low	2.9	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity Nitro group ^f
7k	Low	2.9	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity Nitro group ^f

7l	High	3.7	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity
7m	Low	2.9	Yes	0.55	0 alert	Solubility Lipophilicity

^a GIA = gastrointestinal absorption [11,12]; ^b BBB score = blood-brain barrier permeation prediction [9]; ^c All compounds showed 0 violation against Lipinski's rule of five [13]; ^d Bio. Score = Abbott bioavailability score [14]; ^e PAINS = Pan Assay Interference Structures [15]; ^f Structural alert according to [16].

Figure S2. The bioavailability radar charts of final derivatives 5–7. The pink middle area represents the optimum range for bioavailability. It sums the lipophilicity (LIPO), size, polarity (POLAR), solubility (INSOLU), saturation, (INSATU), and flexibility (FLEX).

5. Antioxidant properties

The compound **6** was assessed for its antioxidant properties *via* the DPPH (diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) free radical assay. Antioxidant activity was quantified as EC_{50} , representing the concentration of the compound necessary to induce a 50% reduction in DPPH activity, with trolox serving as the standard. The data are detailed in Table S4.

Table S4. Antioxidant efficiency of **6** and control compound trolox.

Name	Structure	Antioxidant efficiency (activity)
		$EC_{50} \pm SEM$ (μM)

6		113.60 ± 3.40
Trolox		16.20 ± 0.42

6. Inhibition of amyloid beta aggregation

7c and **7m** were tested to determine their inhibitory activities against A β ₁₋₄₂ self-induced aggregation.

The results for these selected compounds, alongside doxycycline as a positive control, are presented in Table S5 and Figure S3.

Table S5. Inhibition activities of 7c, 7m, and a positive control doxycycline against self-induced A β ₁₋₄₂ aggregation.

Name	Structure	Inhibition of A β ₁₋₄₂ aggregates ± SEM (%) [*]
7c		≈ 0
7m		≈ 0
Doxycycline		≈ 100

Figure S3. Inhibition of Aβ₁₋₄₂ self-aggregation by 7c, 7m, and a positive control doxycycline.

7. NMR spectra of prepared derivatives

Figure S4. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of compound **8**

Figure S5. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound **11**

Figure S6. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of compound **12**

Figure S7. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of compound **13**.

Figure S8. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 5a

Figure S9. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **5b**

Figure S10. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **5c**

Figure S11. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 5d

Figure S12. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 6

Figure S13. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7a**

Figure S14. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7b**

Figure S15. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 7c

Figure S16. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7d**

Figure S17. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 7e

Figure S18. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **7f**

Figure S19. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7g**

Figure S20. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7h**

Figure S21. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **7i**

Figure S22. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7j**

Figure S23. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7k**

Figure S24. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of **7I**

Figure S25. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of **7m**

8. HPLC-MS spectra of prepared compounds

Figure S26. HPLC-MS of compound 8 a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S27. HPLC-MS of compound **13** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S28. HPLC-MS of compound **5a** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S29. HPLC-MS of compound **5b** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S30. HPLC-MS of compound **5c** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S31. HPLC-MS of compound **5d** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S32. HPLC-MS of compound 6 a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S33. HPLC-MS of compound **7a** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S34. HPLC-MS of compound **7b** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S35. HPLC-MS of compound **7c** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S36. HPLC-MS of compound **7d** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S37. HPLC-MS of compound **7e** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S38. HPLC-MS of compound **7f** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S39. HPLC-MS of compound **7g** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S40. HPLC-MS of compound **7h** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S41. HPLC-MS of compound **7i** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S42. HPLC-MS of compound **7j** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S43. HPLC-MS of compound **7k** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S44. HPLC-MS of compound **71** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

Figure S45. HPLC-MS of compound **7m** a) LC-UV chromatogram b) HRMS mass spectra

9. Supporting data for *in silico* studies

Figure S46. (A) The crystal structure of THA (blue) bound to BChE active site (PDB ID: 4BDS) [17]. (B) Top-scored docking pose of tacrine (yellow) in the BChE active. (C) Superimposed structure of crystal and docked tacrine molecule with adjacent amino acid residues. The figure was created with The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, v. 2.5.2.

In Figure S47, the analysis of MD trajectories obtained after 50 ns simulation of compounds **5b**, **5d**, tacrine and amiridine at the binding site of BChE is displayed. Based on the results, we can deduce that root mean square deviations (RMSD) for all heavy atoms atoms of the enzyme reaches roughly plateau values towards to the end of the simulations. From the obtained curve, the amiridine position was stable during the simulation, the amiridine-memantine derivative **5d** position was stabilized after ~25 ns of simulation and maintained the stability until the end of the simulation with a small fluctuation before the end. The amiridine-memantine **5b** was quickly stabilized after about 1-2 ns. Tacrine position was also stabilized after about 5 ns.

Figure S47. Time evolution for enzyme heavy atoms in root mean square deviations (RMSD) upon tacrine, amiridine, **5d** and **5b** binding.

Table S6. The binding energies estimated from MM/MD simulation calculated for top-ranked poses of amiridine, tacrine, **5d** and **5b**. Total interaction energy is the sum of Coulombic interaction energy with Lennard-Jones energy.

ligand	Coulombic interaction energy				Lennard-Jones energy				Total interaction energy			
	Average	Err.Est.	RMSD	Tot-Drift	Average	Err.Est.	RMSD	Tot-Drift		Average	Err.Est.	
amiridine	-70.5818	2.2	14.6795	-14.5118	-107.709	0.35	7.13544	-2.49983	kJ/mol	-178.291	2.227667	kJ/mol
5d	-73.4798	2.7	13.2619	17.4379	-202.406	2.3	12.1981	-12.237	kJ/mol	-275.886	3.54683	kJ/mol
5b	-140.423	2.6	17.925	-3.59297	-206.721	2.6	13.6413	12.9752	kJ/mol	-347.144	3.676955	kJ/mol
tacrine	-82.2024	13	34.9023	-75.0022	-106.843	1.1	8.15147	-1.55005	kJ/mol	-189.045	13.04646	kJ/mol

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